
Classroom Structuring in the 21st Century and Teaching Allegories of Teachers in Public Elementary Schools

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Overview— This study determined and described the classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary school in Tugbok District, Davao City. This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlational method. The respondents of this study were composed of 109 teachers in public elementary school using the universal sampling. The data analysis utilized the mean, pearson r and regression analysis. The findings disclosed that the classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of mastery of the subject matter, classroom setting, art of questioning, evaluation and feedback were manifested oftentimes by the teachers. Moreover, learning allegories of teachers in terms of reflection, expectations, values integration and discovery were manifested oftentimes. It was found out that there was a significant relationship between classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public in public elementary schools. It revealed further that the domains of classroom structuring in the 21st century significantly influenced the teaching allegories of teachers. Based on the findings, the public-school teachers should attend conferences and trainings from the DepEd for professional augmentation program. This may provide proficient improvement for teachers with the goal of building capacity thoroughly supported education opportunities for learners and concurrently learn the content of healthier academic practices.

Keywords— Classroom structuring , teaching allegories, 21st Century, professional augmentation

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching allegories is highly complex process about which people know very little. But one thing they know for sure is that people learn in different ways. How can they have sense of the way the students learn by not just by listening to what they say? A very practical approach is to take note of the allegories in their language. In New York University, the innovative and mind-expanding in teaching allegories in some Europe universities according to linguist Lakoff and philosopher Johnson, (2012) they said that the essence of teaching allegory is understanding and experiencing one kind of thing in terms of another for number of reasons which lead to the problems and doubts in the classroom's discussion situation. It recognizes that learning metaphor is about capturing the essential nature of an experience. For instance, when a student described the situation as it is like they are banging their head against a brick wall, the sense of the repetitive, painful and self-defeating nature of his experience was instantly apparent. Teaching allegory is an active process which is at the very heart of understanding of the teacher, students and the school heads is all about

the teaching process of learning. Teaching allegory need not be limited to verbal expressions. For teacher, teaching allegory can include any expression or thing that is symbolic for a person, it could be that nonverbal behavior, self-produced art, an item in the environment, or an imaginative representation. In other words, whatever a person says, sees, hears, feels or does, as well as what they imagine, can be used to produce, comprehend and reason through learning metaphor. Teaching allegory is not an occasional foray into the world of figurative language, but the fundamental basis for everyday cognition, (Edwards, 2017). In the preceded study of Lakoff and Johnson stated that in all aspects of life, people define their reality in terms of teaching allegories and the proceed to act on the basis of the learning allegories. They draw inferences, set goals, make commitments, and execute plans, all based on how they are a part of the structure in the experiences, consciously and unconsciously, by means of teaching allegories that sometimes lead to the problem of misunderstanding in the classroom due to differences of individual views. In the study of Ortony (2012) it was identified that the characteristics of teaching allegories is the account for their utility these are the vividness, compactness and expressibility. In short, teaching allegories carry a great deal of abstract and intangible information in a concise and memorable package. It is one which most impacts the way students learn. Because learning allegories describe one ex-

perience in terms of another, they specify and constrain the ways of thinking about the original experience. In the Philippines, (Gupata, 2016) cited that there is a very simple way to discover the student's metaphors for learning by just asking the clean language questions are taken from a method of exploring a person's metaphors devised by Grove, (2012), that are fully explained in teaching allegories in mind like transformation through symbolic modelling. Psychotherapist Grove (2011) realized that many of his clients naturally described their symptoms and outcomes in learning allegory. It was discovered that when they enquired about these teaching allegories using the client's exact words, their perception of their problems began to change. The led them to create clean language, a method of asking simple questions of client's teaching allegories which neither contaminate nor distort them. The researcher was motivated to conduct this study to examine closely the structured classroom of teachers in the classroom setting. This study was investigated the structured classroom and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary school. The theory behind this study reiterates the predictions that successful teacher and student interaction in the classroom is essential to the educational and social development of students and the teachers' understanding of their own behavior and practices are therefore of paramount importance in classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories.

a. Review of Significant Literature

Classroom structuring is essential for managing a positive learning environment. Ahmad (2011) emphasizes that effective instruction alone is insufficient; rather, classroom structuring should encourage appropriate behavior and reduce inappropriate conduct. Evertson et al. (2013) recommend clear, daily displays of norms and materials to reinforce structure for both students and teachers.

Effective setups vary by activity. Angelo and Cross (2013) advocate for layouts, such as rows or circles, which help control and foster engagement, while Evertson and Weinstein (2016) suggest group arrangements to facilitate collaboration. Teaching allegories, as Charles (2010) discusses, can shape perceptions and enhance learning, helping teachers adapt to students' cognitive processes. Gupata (2016) and Grove (2012) add that examining students' metaphors helps teachers understand their learning perspectives.

Mastery of subject matter and questioning strategies are vital. Murray and Staebler (2014) note that students respect teachers with deep subject knowledge, while DiGiulio (2010) underscores the importance of developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Barnard (2012) and Borich (2017) emphasize teaching methods that connect theory with practical applications, promoting analytical and conceptual growth. Kounin (2010) highlights "wittiness"—a teacher's ability to monitor students subtly—to prevent disruptions.

The art of questioning, as Michaelsen et al. (2012) outline, guides student understanding by encouraging deeper engagement. Reflective questions foster critical thinking, a point further supported by Bloom et al. (2010). Teachers like Barnes et al. (2014) see questioning as essential in developing students' interpretive abilities, while Evertson and Wein-

stein (2016) stress questioning's role in fostering respectful dialogue.

Evaluation and feedback are crucial for growth. Charles (2010) describes evaluation as key in identifying student needs, while Beech and Domer (2012) recommend varied assessment types to encourage progress. Feedback, as Ramaprasad (2013) explains, closes learning gaps and motivates students to improve. Gupata (2016) further notes feedback's influence on emotional and academic performance.

Teaching allegories are metaphors that guide teacher-student interaction. Edwards and Clifford (2017) suggest that teachers who view students as nurturable entities create more positive learning experiences. Lawley and Tompkins (2012) propose that teachers adopt metaphors that align with their educational philosophy to enhance learning outcomes.

Reflection and values integration play significant roles in teaching effectiveness. Borich (2017) advocates for values integration, encouraging students to see personal relevance in learning. Values-focused teaching promotes moral development, as Brown and Thornton Jr. (2013) argue, helping students understand their broader role in society. Marzano (2015) concludes that holistic values integration fosters both academic and spiritual growth.

b. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored on the theory of Evertson (2013), who stated that in the 21st Century classroom structuring, teachers are facilitators of student learning and creators of productive classroom environments in which students can develop the skills they will need in the workplace. The interdisciplinary nature of the 21st Century classroom structures it apart from the 20th Century classroom. This is supported by the theory of (Charles, 2010) who said that the teachers should be able to see the learning allegories embody and define the intangible and abstract inevitably constrains perceptions and actions to those which make sense within the logic of the teaching allegories. Teaching allegories are therefore both descriptive and perspective. As teachers become aware of their own allegories for learning they can recognize how these limits or liberate them. In this way they can learn from their own learning processes. Considering the theories mentioned, this study further conceptualizes that the classroom structuring and learning allegories of teachers in public elementary school in Tugbok District, Davao City are composed of independent variable and dependent variable. The independent variable is classroom structuring with four indicators such as mastery of the subject matter, classroom setting, art of questioning, evaluation and feedback (Evertson, 2013). The dependent variable is the teaching allegories of teachers like reflection, expectations, values integration and discovery (Simons, 2008). Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study. Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study.

c. Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study was to determine the level of classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary school in Tugbok District, Davao City. Specifically, this study sought to answers the

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

following questions:

1. What is the level of classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of:
 - (a) mastery of the subject matter,
 - (b) classroom setting,
 - (c) art of questioning,
 - (d) evaluation, and
 - (e) feedback?
2. What is the level of learning allegories in terms of:
 - (a) reflection,
 - (b) expectations,
 - (c) values integration, and
 - (d) discovery?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching of teachers in public elementary schools?
4. Which domains of classroom structuring in the 21st century significantly influence teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary schools?

II. METHODOLOGY

This chapter contains the discussion on the following: research design, research participants, research instruments, data gathering procedure, data analysis and other sources of information and data treatment on the relationship of classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary schools in Tugbok District, Davao City.

a. Research Design

This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlation-method. This method was used when the objective is to describe the status of the situation as it existed at the time of the study to explore that causes of a particular phenomenon. In correlation research, it involves collecting data that determined whether the degree of a relationship existed between two or more quantifiable variables (Travers, 2016). Quantitative research design is aimed at discovering how many people think, act or feel in a specific way. Quantitative method involves large sample sizes, concentrating on the quantity of responses, as opposed to gaining the more focused or emotional insight that is the aim of qualitative research. The standard format in quantitative research design is for each respondent to be asked the same questions, which ensures that the entire data sample can be analyzed fairly. The data is supplied in a numerical format and can be analyzed in a quantifiable way using statistical methods. Surveys can, however, be tailored to branch off if the respondent answers in a certain way for instance people who are satisfied or dissatisfied with a service may be asked different questions subsequently. This descriptive survey dealt on quantitative data about the said phenomenon. The quantitative aspect is an appropriate schedule for gathering the data that would be designed for the target respondents to answer the questions. The process of gathering the data was based using questionnaires. The focus of the study determines the relationship between the relationship of classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary school in Tugbok District, Davao City.

b. Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were 109 teachers in Tugbok District, Davao City, they evaluated the relationship of classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary school through the researcher made test questionnaire that were administered to them by the researcher. There were 23 respondents in Vinzons Eementary School, 14 respondents in Tagakpan Elementary School, 15 respondents in Ula Elementary School, 17 respondents in Biao Elementary School, 13 respondents in New Valencia Integrated School, and 11 respondents in Talandang Elementary School. The teachers involved served at least three years in public elementary school. This study was conducted from 2023-2024. The researcher used the universal sampling process in selecting the respondents wherein all the teachers in school were considered as the actual respondents.

c. Research Instruments

The research instruments were used in gathering the date were based on various authors. The questionnaire was contextualized to the local setting. Refinement of the questionnaire were made possible through the assistance of the research adviser and other three research validators who evaluated the content of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was composed of 45 items. There are 9 indicators in this study. Each indicator was made up of 5 item questions. Likert's scale was adopted to determine the relationship of class-

room structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary school in Tugbok District, Davao City. To test for reliability and validity, the instrument was tried out among 22 teachers in one separate school in the same district particularly in Prisco D. Diolosa Elementary School. The instrument was found to be highly reliable with a Cronbach's Alpha result of .734. the instruments used in this study contained two parts and they are as follows: Part 1 dealt with the classroom structuring in public elementary school with five indicators such as mastery of the subject matter, classroom setting, art of questioning, evaluation and feedback which is adopted by (Evertson, 2013).

d. Data Gathering Procedure

The data were gathered through the following procedures: A letter of permission was secured to conduct the study for the relationship of classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers of teachers in public elementary school in Tugbok District, Davao City. The letter of permission and appearance was signed and granted by the Adviser and School Principal, Head Teachers in Tugbok District, Davao City. Adequate and clear copies were printed to avoid problems with the administration. The researcher administered the questionnaire personally to the respondents of the study and they were required to answer the questionnaire honestly so that valid and reliable data should be elicited. The results were collated and tabulated before subjecting it to statistical treatment and analyzed and interpreted based on the purpose of the study.

e. Data Analysis

The gathered data classified, analyzed and interpreted by using the following statistical tools: Mean was used to determine the relationship of classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary school. Pearson Product Moment Correlation or Pearson r was used to find out the significant relationship of classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers. Regression Analysis. This was used to determine the influences between classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary school in Tugbok District, Davao City.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Presented in this chapter are the analysis interpretation and the findings of the data gathered from the research instruments used in the study concerning the classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary schools in Tugbok District, Davao City. This discussion was answered based on the statement of the problems.

a. Classroom Structuring in Terms of Mastery of the Subject Matter

Shown in table 3 is the data on the level of classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of mastery of the subject matter. The mean ratings are arranged from highest to lowest as follows: being knowledgeable in the subject

Scale for Classroom Structuring

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	Classroom structuring of public elementary school is always manifested in school.
3.40-4.19	High	Classroom structuring of public elementary school is oftentimes manifested in school.
2.60-3.39	Moderate	Classroom structuring of public elementary school is occasionally manifested in school.
1.80-2.59	Low	Classroom structuring of public elementary school is seldom manifested in school.
1.00-1.79	Very Low	Classroom structuring of public elementary school is never manifested in school.

TABLE 1: SCALE FOR CLASSROOM STRUCTURING

matter (4.01); being expert in their skills in teaching the subject (3.61) and always meet the objectives everyday in the class (3.28).

Collectively, the overall mean rating is 3.57 or high. This means that classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of mastery of the subject matter was oftentimes manifested by the teachers. This indicates that teachers should strive to become eminent scholars as a necessity for effective classroom management. All good classroom teachers have mastery over the content taught by them. The students are expected to know the level of knowledge a teacher possesses. Generally, they respect the knowledge. The students are found to create no problems in classes of eminent scholars. All teachers should strive to become eminent scholars as a necessity for effective classroom management (Murray and Steabler, 2014). The challenge for the teachers is to guide students to acquire high level learning skills and expertise which characterise their interest to study. Current interest in the development of generic learning skills can provide attention from the central role of the mastery of a coherent body of knowledge on which the generic learning skills can be built (DiGuilio, 2010).

b. Classroom Setting

Reflected in Table 4 is the data on the level of classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of classroom setting. The mean rating are as follows: having participative methods that is fitted to my subject (4.03), having conceptual method that is fitted to my subject (3.73), having interactive method that is fitted to my subject (3.68). The overall mean rating is (3.80) or high. This means that classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of mastery of the classroom setting are oftentimes manifested by the teachers. This indicates the teachers are using participatory methods to be very much effective in making the classroom setting more interested to the students.

An effective classroom setting involves the use of appropriate methods. The participatory methods are found to be very effective in making all students interested in the lesson. A method suitable for one topic may not be the same for another. A good teacher knows the suitability of a method for a topic. Sometimes, students create problems due to inappropriate methods. The teachers need to take stock of the level of the students and the material resources available at their disposal and decide the best method suitable for teaching a

Scale for Teaching Allegories

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	Learning Allegories of public elementary school is always manifested in school.
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2.60-3.39	Moderate	Learning Allegories of public elementary school is occasionally manifested in school.
1.80-2.59	Low	Learning Allegories of public elementary school is seldom manifested in school.
1.00-1.79	Very Low	Learning Allegories of public elementary school is never manifested in school.

TABLE 2: SCALE FOR TEACHING ALLEGORIES

No	Indicators	Mean (x)	Descriptive Level
	The teacher....		
1.	always ready with the lessons when they enter in the class.	3.31	Moderate
2.	knowledgeable in the subject matter.	4.01	High
3.	expert in their skills in teaching the subject.	3.62	High
4.	integrating the lessons to the real-life situations of the students.	3.65	High
5.	always meet the objectives everyday in the class.	3.27	Moderate
Overall Mean		3.57	High

TABLE 3: CLASSROOM STRUCTURING IN TERMS OF MASTERY OF THE SUBJECT MATTER

topic that can elicit maximum student participation. The best methods make the teacher take the role of guide and a helper (Angelo and Cross, 2013). Wittiness referred to promptness in identifying behavior in the classroom setting. But the teacher must decide whether the classroom setting need to pay attention to such as disruptive behavior of the students. Tanner (2008) reported that classroom setting extinction approach; purposeful withholding of attention could be helpful in case of the undesirable behavior that was momentary, not serious, not dangerous and found in case of students, who are

generally well behaved.

c. Art of Questioning

Displayed in Table 5 is the data on level of classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of art of questioning. The mean rating are as follows: having additional points in the recitation of my student (3.34); having additional points in the oral exam of my students (2.96); having additional points in the good class participation of my stu-

No	Indicators	Mean (x)	Descriptive Level
1	The teacher uses participative methods that fit my subject	4.03	High
2	The teacher uses mentoring methods that fit my subject	3.84	High
3	The teacher uses interactive methods that fit my subject	3.68	High
4	The teacher uses lecture and discussion methods that fit my subject	3.7	High
5	The teacher uses conceptual methods that fit my subject	3.73	High
Overall Mean		3.8	High

TABLE 4: CLASSROOM SETTING

dents for my appropriate reward (2.74).

The overall mean rating is 2.98 or moderate. This means that the classroom setting of teachers in the 21st century in terms of art of questioning is sometimes manifested by the teachers. It indicates that the teacher is designing a questions to drill for rote answers which require little imagination, because mastering the art of questioning teaches students how to think. People begin asking questions almost as early as they begin to speak. Questions solicit information for the purpose of understanding something. Everyday questions are different from the questions effective teachers ask, because effective teachers formulate questions with an eye to increase someone else’s understanding. Lesson plans should take into consideration the importance of questioning in teaching (Michaelsen, Bauman, Knight, Fink, 2012). There are three opportunities to use different types of art of questioning, before students receive a class, during the class, and reflective questions after the class. The importance of questioning in teaching is essential in gauging how well students understand; and classroom questions also give students the opportunity to ask the teacher clarifying questions (Barnes, Christensen, Hansen, 2014).

d. Evaluation

Displayed in Table 6 is the level of evaluation of teachers in the 21st century in terms of evaluation. The mean ratings are as follows: giving role playing activity to the students as part of evaluation yielded a mean rating of (3.58); and giving assignment to the students as part of evaluation earned a mean rating of (3.50). The overall mean rating of (3.54) or high. This means that the teachers’ evaluation is oftentimes manifested. This signifies that the teacher’s evaluation are the systematic determination of a subject’s merit, worth and significance, using criteria governed by a set of standards.

e. Feedback

The high rating of classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of evaluation is parallel to the idea of

Bernard, (2012) which stated that evaluation is a systematic determination of a subject’s merit, worth and significance, using criteria governed by a set of standards. The purpose of an evaluation is to identify areas of difficulty for individual students, to gather data for instructional planning, to assign grades, or to evaluate a program should dictate the kinds of questions asked, the methods employed, and the used of the resulting information. When one type of measure is used in lieu of another, the information obtained is often invalid or useless. In addition, the methods used to gather information should be appropriate to the developmental level and maturity of the students (Charles, 2010). Evaluation is a systematic determination of a subject’s merit, worth and significance, using criteria governed by a set of standards. It can assist an organization to assess any aim, realizable concept/proposal, or any alternative, to help in decision-making; or to ascertain the degree of achievement or value in regard to the aim and objectives and results of any action that has been completed. The primary purpose of evaluation, in addition to gaining insight into prior or existing initiatives, is to enable reflection and assist in the identification of future change (Beech and Domer, 2012).

Illustrated in table 7 is the classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of feedback. The main rating are as follows: delivering the feedback to the student’s behavior yielded a mean rating of (4.59); and elaborating feedback to students’ physical status earned a mean rating of (4.51). The overall mean rating is (3.95) or high.

This means that the feedback of teachers is oftentimes manifested by them. This indicates that the teachers are committed to use feedback to the students for effective school operation which is consistent for classroom policy implementations. The findings conform with the observation of Borich, (2017) that feedback on school activities intervene as necessary accommodating different teacher personalities, styles, and teaching strategies. Feedback is a process in which information about the past of the present influences the same phenomenon in the present or future. As part of a chain of cause-and-effect that forms a circuit or loop, the event is said

No	Indicators	Mean (x)	Descriptive Level
1	Adds additional points for good class participation of students due to appropriate rewards	2.74	Moderate
2	Adds additional points in students' recitation	3.34	Moderate
3	Adds additional points for students' PowerPoint presentations	2.99	Moderate
4	Adds additional points in students' oral exams	2.96	Moderate
5	Adds additional points in students' demonstrations	2.88	Moderate
Overall Mean		2.98	Moderate

TABLE 5: ART OF QUESTIONING

No	Indicators	Mean (x)	Descriptive Level
1	Gives assignments to students as a part of evaluation	3.5	High
2	Gives quizzes to students as a part of evaluation	3.52	High
3	Conducts exams for students as a part of evaluation	3.56	High
4	Gives role-play activities to students as a part of evaluation	3.58	High
5	Assigns projects to students as a part of evaluation	3.56	High
Overall Mean		3.54	High

TABLE 6: EVALUATION

to “feed back” into itself. Ramaprasad (2013) defines feedback generally as “information about the gap between the actual level and the reference level of a system parameter which is used to alter the gap in some way”, emphasizing that the information by itself is not feedback unless translated into action. Self-regulating mechanisms have existed since antiquity, and the idea of feedback had started to enter economic theory in Britain by the eighteenth century, but it was not at that time recognized as a universal abstraction and so didn't have a name. feedback is commonly divided into types – usually termed positive and negative. The terms can be applied in two contexts: the context of the gap is widening (positive) or narrowing (negative); the context of the action or effect that alters the gap, based on whether it has happy (positive) or unhappy (negative) emotional connotation to the recipient

or observer, (Gupata, 2016).

f. Summary on Classroom structuring

Presented in Table 8 is the summary on the level of classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of mastery of the subject matter, classroom setting, art of questioning, evaluation and feedback. The mean ratings of these indicators are as follows: mastery of the subject matter (3.57) or high; classroom setting (3.80) or high; art of questioning (2.98) or high; evaluation (4.54) or very high; and feedback (3.95) or high. The overall mean rating is (3.77) or high. This means that the level of classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of mastery of the subject matter, classroom setting, art of questioning, evaluation, and feed-

No	Indicators	Mean (x)	Descriptive Level
1	Gives feedback on students' intellectual status	4.58	Very High
2	Delivers feedback on students' behavior	4.59	Very High
3	Explains feedback on students' social status	3.5	High
4	Discusses feedback on students' emotional status	3.58	High
5	Elaborates feedback on students' physical status	3.51	High
Overall Mean		3.95	High

TABLE 7: FEEDBACK

back are manifested oftentimes. This signifies that teachers are introducing the structure in the classroom environment, encourage appropriate behavior, and reduce the occurrence of inappropriate behavior for strong classroom management structured classroom.

Classroom structuring could also be considered in classroom management by effective instruction alone that is insufficient for establishing universal classroom management. Classroom structuring gives structure the classroom environment, encourage appropriate behavior, and reduce the occurrence of inappropriate behavior are necessary for strong classroom management structure classroom equally important to the classroom environment and can be considered a separate set of procedure (Ahmad, 2011). Students need daily details in the same place across the team/grade level) date, agenda, assignment, reminders, procedures, 3-5 positively stated norms and specific classroom roles. This is not only necessary for students, but also for teachers. They need to read and see a quote of the day/week/month; college and career symbols famous historical and everyday art and blank boards and walls for students to fill up (Evertson, Emmer, Sanford, Clements, 2013).

g. Reflection

Demonstrated in Table 8 is the level of learning allegories of teachers in terms of reflection. The mean ratings are as follows: meditating models of enthusiasm not only for his subject but also for teaching and learning in general (4.58); reflecting, inspiring and influences students through expert and is innovator who changes strategies, techniques, texts, and materials when better ones are found and/or when existing ones no longer provide a substantive learning experience for her students got a mean rating of (4.51) and contemplating changes strategies, techniques, texts, and materials when better ones are found and/or when existing ones no longer provide a substantive learning experience for her students (2.51). The overall mean rating is (3.55) or high. This means that the learning allegories of teachers in terms

of reflection are oftentimes manifested. This stresses that the teachers are reflecting and communicating strong ideals, beliefs of schooling and cultivating moral virtues towards their staff.

This study is allied to the statement of Brown, (2007) emphasized that learning metaphors reflects effective teaching could assist an individual or group to clarify and address immediate concerns by following a systematic problem-solving process. Learning metaphors of teachers in reflection of effective teaching is a process for providing psychological and educational services in which a specialist works cooperatively with a staff member to improve the learning and adjustment of a student or a group of students. Reflection of effective teaching means having mastery of the subject matter or content. Teachers' primary responsibilities are to represent the content accurately and efficiently. Learner's responsibilities are to learn that content in its authorized or legitimate forms. Reflection of effective teaching is manifested by teachers who take learners systematically through tasks leading to content mastery. Providing clear objectives, adjusting the pace of lecturing, making efficient use of class time, clarifying misunderstanding, answering questions, providing timely feedback, correcting errors, providing reviews, summarizing what has been presented, directing students to appropriate resources, setting high standards for achievement and developing objective means of assessing learning (Ahmad, 2011).

through tasks leading to content mastery. Providing clear objectives, adjusting the pace of lecturing, making efficient use of class time, clarifying misunderstanding, answering questions, providing timely feedback, correcting errors, providing reviews, summarizing what has been presented, directing students to appropriate resources, setting high standards for achievement and developing objective means of assessing learning (Ahmad, 2011).

No	Indicators	Mean (x)	Descriptive Level
1	Mastery of the subject matter	3.57	High
2	Classroom setting	3.8	High
3	Art of questioning	2.98	Moderate
4	Evaluation	4.54	Very High
5	Feedback	3.95	High
Overall Mean		3.95	High

TABLE 8: SUMMARY ON THE LEVEL OF CLASSROOM STRUCTURING

No	Indicators	Mean (x)	Descriptive Level
1	Reflects, inspires, and influences students through expert and referent power but never coercive power.	4.51	Very High
2	Ponders the subject well and is kind and respectful towards students.	4.55	Very High
3	Thinks with greater objectivity in balancing the needs of individuals with the needs of the class as a whole.	2.53	Low
4	Models enthusiasm not only for the subject but also for teaching and learning in general.	3.58	High
5	Contemplates changing strategies, techniques, texts, and materials when better options are found or existing ones no longer provide substantive learning.	2.51	Low
Overall Mean		3.55	High

TABLE 9: REFLECTION

h. Expectations

Demonstrated in table 10 is the level of learning allegories of teachers in terms of clarity of expectation. The mean ratings are as follows: discussing the expectations to the students in the relevance and function of group projects expectations yielded a mean rating of (4.56); and elaborating expectations in the classroom negotiation communication for conflict management and discusses expectations in interpersonal and collaborative skills that are essential or desirable in the classroom gained a mean rating of (4.50). The overall mean rating of (4.32) or very high. This means that the learning metaphors of teachers in terms of expectations are always manifested. This accentuates that the learning metaphors of teachers in terms of expectations are enough to address the personal and professional needs of their staff.

This conforms to the statement of Charles, (2010) that expectations enhance a student's competencies in a specific skill area by providing a process of observation, reflection, and action. Ongoing relationship that can last for a long period of time relationship generally has a set duration. Make sure that students know the teacher expect of them. The classroom rules for the teacher would be presented should be positive, specific and concise. Teacher may wish to post

them in the classroom or distribute them for students to sign. Teacher should also spell out what happen if students do not expectations. Provide students with a discipline-specific context for the development and assessment of group skills (Brown and Thornton, 2013). The closer group tasks resemble authentic tasks, the stronger would students be motivated to learn. Teacher might begin by helping students identify the skills needed in the field of study to work effectively as a group what specific communication, negotiation, conflict management, interpersonal and collaborative skills are essential or desirable? Try the following to help students understand why group skills are important in their field. Emphasize how important group work is for employment. Invite a guest speaker from industry to outline how they use teams in the workplace. Ask students in the class who work part-time or full-time to share their experience of group work, (Brown, 2017).

i. Values Integration

Exhibited in table 11 is the level of learning allegories of teachers in terms of values integration. The mean ratings are as follows: establishing clear objectives for each lesson and works to meet those specific objectives during each

No	Indicators	Mean (x)	Descriptive Level
1	Explains classroom rules clearly, presenting expectations positively, specifically, and concisely.	3.52	High
2	Discusses expectations in discipline-specific contexts for the development and assessment of group skills.	4.54	Very High
3	Communicates the relevance and function of group project expectations to students.	4.56	Very High
4	Elaborates expectations in classroom negotiation and communication for conflict management.	4.5	Very High
5	Discusses interpersonal and collaborative skills essential or desirable in the classroom.	4.5	Very High
Overall Mean		4.32	Very High

TABLE 10: EXPECTATIONS

class and has good classroom management skills and can ensure good student behavior, effective study and work habits, and an overall sense of respect in the classroom yielded a mean rating of (4.58); and has effective discipline skills and can promote positive behaviors and change in the classroom earned a mean rating of (4.52). The overall rating is (4.55) or very high. This means that the learning metaphors of teachers in terms of values integration are always manifested. This highlights that the teachers are integrating the lessons to align the school objectives and provide quality education. It is the starting point of values integration in learning areas and their unique contribution as bodies of knowledge.

This conforms to the statement of Fontana (2015) stated that values integration are effectively and efficiently implemented in the classroom to manage the complexity of everyday life in the classroom that is beneficial for the students to be able to form the classroom improvement. Values Integration is a channel of values development through the teaching-learning activities in the different learning areas. The starting point of values integration is the nature of the learning areas and their unique contribution as bodies of knowledge. Teachers first identify the concepts to be developed in the lesson; then develops the values inherent in the subject (Borich, 2017). Values Integration does not mean quoting a value and discussing it. It is leading the students to see a personal meaning in whatever teachers teach in the classroom. Values integration is more than just teaching the students what is right, it is about promoting within the students perceptions in life such as studying and working hard are acts of worship, to love and forgive each other for the sake of god, to repel evil with good in return, to love for others what they love for themselves and modesty in dress and actions at all times (Charles, 2010). Through education they achieve enlightenment. In the conditions of enlightenment, we make informed choices that become the guiding influences in our lives. The language enriches us and enables us to articulate every thought, idea, observation, feeling or moment we cherish. The language is not the instrument of our intellectual

imprisonment (Brown and Thornton Jr., 2013).

j. Discovery

Elucidated in table 10 is the level of learning allegories of teachers in terms of discovery. The mean ratings are as follows: motivating the students to participate in the learning process and provides an individualized learning experience in the classroom yielded a rating mean of (4.59) and actively engage the students in the learning process gained a rating mean of (4.50). The overall mean rating of (4.20) or very high. This means that the level of learning allegories of teachers in terms of discovery are always manifested. This indicates that the teachers use discovery method to encourage students to become active participants in the learning process by exploring concepts and answering questions through experience in the classroom. It is a discovery of learning promoting a deep understanding for a high level of student engagement.

The high rating of level of learning allegories of teachers in terms of discovery is important as Saab, et al., (2010) suggested that the educational goals of discovery learning include promoting a deep understanding, developing meta-cognitive skills, and encouraging a high level of student engagement.

k. Summary on Learning Allegories

Presented in Table 13 is the summary on the level of learning allegories of teachers in terms of reflection, expectations, values integration and discovery. The mean ratings of these indicators are as follows: reflection (3.55) or high; expectations (4.32) or very high; values integration (4.55) or very high and discovery (4.56) or very high. The overall mean rating of self-concept of neophyte public elementary school teachers in terms of ecological self, interpersonal self, extended self and private self is (4.23) or very high. This means that the level of self-concept of neophyte public elementary school

No	Indicators	Mean (x)	Descriptive Level
1	Engages and holds the attention of students in all discussions, and maintains open communication with parents, keeping them informed of classroom activities, curriculum, discipline, and other concerns.	4.53	Very High
2	Establishes clear objectives for each lesson and works to meet those specific objectives during each class.	4.58	Very High
3	Demonstrates effective discipline skills, promoting positive behaviors and changes in the classroom.	4.52	Very High
4	Has strong classroom management skills, ensuring good student behavior, effective study habits, and an overall sense of respect in the classroom.	4.58	Very High
5	Has incredible knowledge of and enthusiasm for the subject matter being taught.	4.54	Very High
Overall Mean		4.55	Very High

TABLE 11: EXPECTATIONS

No	Indicators	Mean (x)	Descriptive Level
1	Actively engage students in the learning process.	4.5	Very High
2	Motivate students to participate in the learning process.	4.59	Very High
3	Encourage autonomy and independence in students.	4.57	Very High
4	Promote the development of creativity and problem-solving skills in students.	4.56	Very High
5	Provide an individualized learning experience in the classroom.	4.59	Very High
Overall Mean		4.56	Very High

TABLE 12: DISCOVERY

teachers are always manifested. This signifies that teachers are distinguishing among several kinds of self-concept includes self-specifying information and establishing a different aspect of the self.

1. Significant Relationship Between the Classroom Structuring and Teaching Allegories

Presented in Table 12 is the significant relationship between classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary schools with an overall r-value of .006 with equivalent tabular value 0.502 at 0.05 of significance set in this

Since the overall computed value is very much higher than

the tabular value. This indicates that the null hypothesis is hereby rejected, and it could be stated therefore, that there is a significant relationship between the classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary schools. This implies that the higher classroom structuring, the better teaching allegories in public elementary school teachers. Classroom structuring need a daily warm-up activity; active word walls; purposeful posters/boards; and literacy resources (writing/reading materials: books, magazines, newspaper articles). For teacher-focused activities, straight rows facing front; chevron pattern angled to face front are most appropriate and needed when giving/projecting direct information from the front of the classroom. This desk structure provides teacher control

No	Indicators	Mean (x)	Descriptive Level
1	Reflection	3.55	High
2	Clarity of expectations	4.32	Very High
3	Values integration	4.55	Very High
4	Discovery	4.56	Very High
Overall Mean		4.25	Very High

TABLE 13: SUMMARY ON TEACHING ALLEGORIES

Variables	X	Y	r-value	Degree of Correlation	p-value computed	Tabular	Decision <u>(Ho)</u>
Classroom Structuring	4.34		0.060	High Correlation	3.35	0.502	Rejected
Teaching Allegories		4.10					

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). The hypothesis is rejected.

TABLE 14: SIGNIFICANCE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE CLASSROOM STRUCTURING AND TEACHING ALLEGORIES

and lets put certain kids up front (Angelo and Cross, 2013).

Classroom structuring for student-focused activities, whole/semi-circles, triads and quad groups, and rotation stations are necessary when working on collaboration, teamwork, relationship-building, and projects. Those student-focused arrangements are more engaging and active, and they create a structure/control for the social interaction that our students need (Evertson Weinstein, 2016).

m. The Domains of Classroom Structuring Significantly Influence Teaching Allegories

Presented in Table 13 is the domains of classroom structuring in the 21st century significantly influence teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary schools in Tugbok District, Davao City with an overall computed r-value of 0.136 with equivalent tabular value 0.058 at 0.05 of significance set in this study. Since the overall computed value is very much higher that the tabular value. This indicates that the null hypothesis in rejected. This could be stated therefore, that the domains of classroom structuring in the 21st century is significantly influencing the teaching allegories of teachers. This implies that the higher the domains of classroom structuring, the better teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary school in Tugbok District, Davao City.

Classroom structuring could also be considered in classroom management by effective instruction alone that is insufficient for establishing universal classroom management. Instructional practices that structure the classroom environment, encourage appropriate behavior, and reduce the occurrence of inappropriate behavior are necessary for strong classroom management structured classroom equally important to the classroom environment and can be considered a separate set of procedures (Ahmad, 2011). Students need daily details in the same place (across the team/grade level):date, agenda, assignment, reminders, procedures, 3-5 positively-stated norms (not rules); and specific classroom roles. This is not only necessary for students, but also for teachers. They need to read and see a quote of the day/week/month; college and career symbols (i.e., diploma, pennant, shirt); famous historical and everyday heroes (i.e., students!) in each content area; individual and team awards; famous and everyday art; and blank boards and walls for students to fill up (Evertson, Emmer, Sanford, Clements, 2013).

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Presented in this chapter are the summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations of the study on the classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories

<i>Model</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Degrees of Freedom</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Decision</i>
	55.3897	1	57.029			
<i>Regression</i>	503.302	108	12.5947	0.58	0.136	<i>Rejected</i>
<i>Residual Total</i>	535.101	109				

Note: Significance when $P < 0.05$ (2T)

TABLE 15: THE DOMAINS OF CLASSROOM STRUCTURING SIGNIFICANTLY INFLUENCE TEACHING ALLEGORIES

of teachers in public elementary schools in Tugbok District, Davao City. The purpose of this study was to determine the level of classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary school in Tugbok District, Davao City. This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlation-method. The following were the salient findings of the study. The classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of mastery of the subject matter, classroom setting, art of questioning, evaluation and feedback was high and oftentimes manifested. This signified that teachers are introducing the structure in the classroom environment, encourage appropriate behavior, and reduce the occurrence of inappropriate behavior for strong classroom management structured classroom. The level of learning allegories of teachers in terms of reflection, expectations, values integration and discovery was very high and always manifested. This signifies that teacher is distinguishing among several kinds of self-concept includes self-specifying information and establishing a different aspect of the self. The overall computed value was very much higher than the tabular value. This indicates that the null hypothesis was rejected. This could be stated therefore, that there is a significant relationship between the classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary school. This implied that the higher result of the classroom structuring, the better teaching allegories of public elementary schools' teachers. The overall computed value was very much higher than the tabular value. This indicated that the null hypothesis was rejected. This could be stated therefore, that the domains of classroom structuring in the 21st century was significantly influencing the teaching allegories of teachers. This implied that the higher the result of the domains of classroom structuring, the better teaching allegories of teachers in public schools in Tugbok District, Davao City.

a. Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn: It was concluded in this study that the level of classroom structuring of teachers in the 21st century in terms of mastery of the subject matter, classroom setting, art of questioning, evaluation and feedback was high and manifested oftentimes by the teachers. It was established in this study that the level of learning allegories of teachers in terms of reflection, expectations, values integration and discovery was very high and always manifested by the teachers. It was concluded in this study that there was a significant relationship between the classroom structuring in the 21st cen-

tury and teaching allegories of teachers in public elementary schools. It was concluded in this study that the domains of classroom structuring in the 21st century was significantly influenced the teaching allegories of teachers.

b. Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are formulated for considerations: It is recommended in this study that classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers may be improved by the Department of Education mainly on the portion of gray areas which are the teacher should always meet the objectives everyday in the class, always ready with the lessons when they enter in the class, conceptual method that is fitted to the subject and lecture and discussion method that is fitted to the subject. It is mentioned in this study that the classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers may be enriched by the teachers mostly on the part of gray areas which are additional points in the good class participation of the students with appropriate rewards and gives assignment to the students as part of evaluation. It is recommended in this study that the classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers may be upgraded by the school heads particularly in the low result areas of the study such as explaining the feedback to the students social status and contemplates changed strategies, techniques, texts, and materials when better ones are found and/or when existing ones no longer provide a substantive learning experience for the students. It is acclaimed in this study that the classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers may be improved by the school heads primarily in the low result areas of the study such as explains expectation in the classroom rules clearly and present it positively, specifically and concisely and engages and holds the attention of students in all discussions and maintains open communication with parents and keeps them informed of what is going on in the classroom as far as curriculum, discipline, and other issues concerned. It is recommended in this study that the future researchers should make a starting point how to expand and to develop more coverage of the research on terms of the classroom structuring in the 21st century and teaching allegories of teachers.

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